

NPK Effect on Growth of *Capsicum frutescens* L. by Seed Hydropriming Method

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Abstract

This experiment was conducted at the Department of Botany, Bago University. The paper presents the results of studies on the seed germination and the influence of different rates of NPK fertilizers in priming and nonpriming seeds of *Capsicum frutescens* (L.). The mean values of germination percentage were computed. The highest percentage of germination was recorded when seeds were treated with water. This experiment evaluated the comparative responses between priming and nonpriming seedlings of *Capsicum frutescens* (L.) to rates of NPK (0g, 5g, 10g) fertilizer application. Data collected included plant growth parameters such as plant height, number of leaves, area of leaves per plant, leaf development, fresh weight and dry weight of plant. When compared the nonpriming plants and priming plants, the priming plants had superior agronomic characters than nonpriming plants. Among the treatments of NPK fertilizer application on priming and nonpriming plants, it was shown that T₄ (priming + NPK 5g) had an effect on vegetative growths.

Introduction

Pepper (*Capsicum* sp.) belongs to the family Solanaceae (Heiser, C. B., 1976). It grows in tropical, subtropical as well as temperate regions. Pepper, rich in vitamins A, C and E is being used as a food flavoring, a coloring agent, a pharmaceutical ingredient (Purseglove *et al.*, 1981). Chilli crop (*Capsicum frutescens* L.) is one of many important vegetable crops being cultivated in most Asian countries such as the Philippines, Myanmar, India, Laos, Cambodia, Malaysia, Thailand and many others. (Suksri *et al.*, 1999).

In Myanmar, pepper is an important vegetable and major spice crop with considerable economic importance. Myanmar people, pods of chili plants both fresh and dry are commonly used in many cooking recipes as to achieve a tasty daily food with high in both palatability and nutritious values. One of the most important problems facing the farmers in developing countries is heterogeneity and lack of suitable conditions in soil that causes decreasing in germination percent, heterogeneous emergence, unbalanced seedling growth and competition for environmental resources such as light, nutrients and water (Roa and Philipse, 1993). One of the methods that can overcome this problem is seed preplanting treatments called priming that include water absorption at enough level to begin germination percent, decreasing mean of germination time and improving growth and vigor of seedling at very wide favor and unfavorable environmental conditions. This method is successful in small seed plants that have great economic value with quick and uniform emergence requirement (Ellis and Roberts, 1981). Seed priming accelerates seed germination and seedling establishment under both normal and stressful environments (Ashraf, M., MR. Foolad, 2005). Priming is one of the physiological methods, which improves seed performance and provides faster and synchronized germination (Sivritepe, H. O. and A. M. Dourado, 1995). Hydropriming is the simplest approach to hydrate seeds and minimize the use of chemicals.

The seed in each pod depended most on the ratio between nitrogen and potassium in soil being applied for crop cultivation, i.e, the higher the amount of nitrogen (N) in soil

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than potassium (K) the hotter the taste in matured pods, yet a reverse taste could be found if K in soil is much higher than N (Suksri, 1999).

The objectives of this research is to know the germination rate of nonpriming and priming of seeds and to know the effect of NPK fertilizers on growth of *Capsicum frutescens* L.

Materials and Methods

The Study Site

The experiment was set up in pots, Department of Botany, Bago University.

Materials

The materials used in this experiment was as follows, 200 seeds of chili pepper, taken from Bago Market, 24 polythylene bag (19.5 cm × 13.0 cm), spray bottle, plastic basket (30 cm × 23 cm), a digital balance, a pencil, a scissor, hand paper sheet (20 cm × 20 cm), an oven, NPK fertilizers (15:15:15).

Preparing Soil Medium for Seed Germination

The germination of chili pepper was set up under the shade. The sand, burnt and humus were mixed in a ratio of 1:1:1. Then the soil medium was watered and left the prepared soil for a week before sowing the seed.

Planting Design

In this experiment six treatments with four replicates were set up Completely Randomized Design (CRD). The distance between individual bag and between the rows is 1 ft apart. The treatments were as follows;

- T₁ = Non-priming
 T₂ = Priming
 T₃ = Nonpriming + 5g of NPK
 T₄ = Priming + 5g of NPK
 T₅ = Nonpriming + 10g of NPK
 T₆ = Priming + 10g of NPK

NPR ₁	NP ₅ R ₄	P ₁₀ R ₃	PR ₁	NP ₁₀ R ₂	P ₅ R ₃
P ₅ R ₄	PR ₂	NPR ₂	NP ₁₀ R ₁	P ₁₀ R ₄	NP ₅ R ₃
NP ₅ R ₂	NP ₁₀ R ₃	PR ₄	P ₅ R ₁	NPR ₃	P ₁₀ R ₁
NP ₁₀ R ₄	NPR ₄	NP ₅ R ₁	P ₁₀ R ₂	P ₅ R ₂	PR ₃

Figure 1. The Map of Bago University

(a) Seeds sample soaking in water

(b) Digital balance

(c) Polyethylene bag

(d) Sample of seeds

(e) Oven

(f) Fruit sample

Figure 2. Material used for experiments

Figure 3. Soil preparation

Priming

Nonpriming

Figure 4. Sowing the seeds

Priming

Nonpriming

Figure 5. (a) Germinated seeds

Priming

Nonpriming

Figure 6. The stages of growth in 30DAS of seedlings

Figure 7. Transplanted plants in polyethylene bags

Figure 8. Measurements of plant Height, leaf length and leaf width

Figure 9. Comparison of vegetative growth in nonpriming and priming of *Capsicum frutescens* L (57 DAS)

Figure 10. Vegetative growth in nonpriming and priming of *Capsicum frutescens* L (85DAS)

Paper leaf

All leaves

3 leaf

Root

Stem

Figure 11. Weighting of fresh weight

Figure 12. Dried the plants in oven

Results

Classification of *Capsicum*

The genus *Capsicum* belongs to the order Solanales in the family Solanaceae, which is a family of mainly tropical species (Cronquist, 1981).

Division	:	Magnoliidae
Class	:	Eudicots
Subclass	:	Asterids
Order	:	Solanales
Family	:	Solanaceae
Sub-family	:	Solanoidea
Genus	:	<i>Capsicum</i>
Species	:	<i>frutescens</i>
Scientific name	:	<i>Capsicum frutescens</i> L.

Morphological Characters of *Capsicum frutescens* L.

Mesophytic annual herbs. Stem aerial, erect, herbaceous, cylindrical, glabrous, branched. Leaves alternate, simple, petiolate, exstipulate, ovate, elliptic to narrowly lanceolate, cauline and reticulate venation. Inflorescence cymes, axillary or terminal. Flowers white, bracteate, ebracteolate, pedicellate, complete, bisexual, actinomorphic, pentamerous, hypogynous; sepals 5, gamosepalous, campanulate, persistent, sepaloid, valvate; petals 5, gamopetalous, rotate, white, valvate; stamens 5, epipetalous, unequal, longitudinal dehiscences; ovary superior, bicarpellary, syncarpous, bilocular, style simple, stigma capitate. Fruits berry, indehiscent, pungent to taste. Seeds small, flat, endospermic.

Table 1. Germination Number of Seeds

Treatment	Replicaton	Germination perdays (DAS)																													
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30
Nonpriming	R ₁	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	6	14	21	25	32	36	39	43	46	52	55	58	61	61	61	61	61	61	61
	R ₂	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	7	10	15	20	26	31	35	39	42	47	51	54	57	60	62	62	62	62	62	62
Priming	R ₁	-	-	-	-	-	8	14	22	26	31	36	40	46	49	53	57	62	68	70	75	81	87	91	96	97	97	97	97	97	
	R ₂	-	-	-	-	-	9	15	22	28	30	37	41	47	52	58	63	69	73	78	84	88	92	95	97	98	98	98	98	98	

Table 2. Germination Rate of Nonpriming and Priming

Treatments	Germination Rate (%)
Priming	97.5
Nonpriming	61.5

Figure 13. Germination Rate of Nonpriming and Priming

Table 3. Plant Height (cm) of Nonpriming and Priming (57 DAS)

Treatment	36 DAS	43 DAS	50 DAS	57 DAS
T ₁ (nonpriming)	3.25	7.75	14.25	19.25
T ₂ (priming)	3.25	11.83	16.23	21.63
T ₃ (nonpriming + NPK 5 g)	2.63	7.25	14.3	18.5
T ₄ (priming + NPK 5 g)	2.86	10.13	17.63	23.15
T ₅ (nonpriming + NPK 10 g)	2.5	6.15	10.4	14.0
T ₆ (priming + NPK 10 g)	2.68	9.95	16.38	21.13

Figure 14. Plant Height (cm) of Nonpriming and Priming (57 DAS)

Table 4. Plant Height (cm) of Nonpriming and Priming (85 DAS)

Treatment	64 DAS	71 DAS	78 DAS	85 DAS
T ₁ (nonpriming)	24.5	35.38	54.0	67.38
T ₂ (priming)	30.13	42.5	61.25	68.75
T ₃ (nonpriming + NPK 5 g)	22.86	33.25	48.75	68.0
T ₄ (priming + NPK 5 g)	30.125	45.63	64.75	75.38
T ₅ (nonpriming + NPK 10 g)	17.08	24.33	35.88	51.88
T ₆ (priming + NPK 10 g)	28.33	42.5	57.63	68.88

Figure 15. Plant Height (cm) of Nonpriming and Priming (85 DAS)

Table 5. Number of Leaf Per Plant (57 DAS)

Treatment	36 DAS	43 DAS	50 DAS	57 DAS
T ₁ (nonpriming)	4	9	13	17
T ₂ (priming)	5	9	14	15
T ₃ (nonpriming + NPK 5 g)	5	9	13	16
T ₄ (priming + NPK 5 g)	5	9	14	15
T ₅ (nonpriming + NPK 10 g)	4	8	10	15
T ₆ (priming + NPK 10 g)	5	9	13	12

Figure 16. Number of Leaf Per Plant of Nonpriming and Priming (57 DAS)

Table 6. Number of Leaf Per Plant (85 DAS)

Treatment	64 DAS	71 DAS	78 DAS	85 DAS
T ₁ (nonpriming)	24	104	123	175
T ₂ (priming)	25	55	68	82
T ₃ (nonpriming + NPK 5 g)	73	73	95	144
T ₄ (priming + NPK 5 g)	28	62	95	94
T ₅ (nonpriming + NPK 10 g)	17	35	46	89
T ₆ (priming + NPK 10 g)	25	58	67	84

Figure 17. Number of Leaf Per Plant of Nonpriming and Priming (85 DAS)

Table 7. Leaf Length (cm) of Nonpriming and Priming (57 DAS)

Treatment	36 DAS	43 DAS	50 DAS	57 DAS
T ₁ (nonpriming)	4.6	5.18	5.58	5.85
T ₂ (priming)	5.6	7.03	8.25	8.78
T ₃ (nonpriming + NPK 5 g)	4.75	5.55	6.1	6.5
T ₄ (priming + NPK 5 g)	5.33	7.5	7.85	9.01
T ₅ (nonpriming + NPK 10 g)	3.65	4.63	5.15	5.75
T ₆ (priming + NPK 10 g)	3.88	6.03	6.58	6.95

Figure 18. Leaf Length (cm) of Nonpriming and Priming (57 DAS)

Table 8. Leaf Length (cm) of Nonpriming and Priming (85 DAS)

Treatment	64 DAS	71 DAS	78 DAS	85 DAS
T ₁ (nonpriming)	8.5	9.08	9.48	9.73
T ₂ (priming)	8.98	9.85	10.1	10.63
T ₃ (nonpriming + NPK 5 g)	8.03	9.03	9.6	10.0
T ₄ (priming + NPK 5 g)	9.48	10.58	11.3	11.68
T ₅ (nonpriming + NPK 10 g)	5.9	6.7	7.18	7.6
T ₆ (priming + NPK 10 g)	8.8	10.83	10.28	11.03

Figure 19. Leaf Length (cm) of Nonpriming and Priming (85 DAS)

Table 9. Leaf Width (cm) of Nonpriming and Priming (57 DAS)

Treatment	36 DAS	43 DAS	50 DAS	57 DAS
T ₁ (nonpriming)	2.4	2.63	2.78	2.7
T ₂ (priming)	3.7	4.08	4.28	2.38
T ₃ (nonpriming + NPK 5 g)	2.38	2.83	3.0	3.18
T ₄ (priming + NPK 5 g)	3.03	3.83	4.18	4.43
T ₅ (nonpriming + NPK 10 g)	1.95	2.45	2.63	3.1
T ₆ (priming + NPK 10 g)	2.08	3.1	3.38	3.6

Figure 20. Leaf Width (cm) of Nonpriming and Priming (57 DAS)

Table 10. Leaf Width (cm) of Nonpriming and Priming (85 DAS)

Treatment	64 DAS	71 DAS	78 DAS	85 DAS
T ₁ (nonpriming)	3.38	3.63	3.73	3.88
T ₂ (priming)	5.15	6.18	6.63	6.93
T ₃ (nonpriming + NPK 5 g)	2.68	3.8	3.98	4.35
T ₄ (priming + NPK 5 g)	5.33	6.08	6.45	7.43
T ₅ (nonpriming + NPK 10 g)	2.55	2.95	3.13	3.3
T ₆ (priming + NPK 10 g)	5.3	6.13	6.43	6.7

Figure 21. Leaf Width (cm) of Nonpriming and Priming (85 DAS)

Table 11. Leaf Area (cm ²) for 57 DAS and 85 DAS		
Treatment	57 DAS	85 DAS
T ₁ (nonpriming)	40.76	83.32
T ₂ (priming)	47.84	91.12
T ₃ (nonpriming + NPK 5 g)	47.14	103.708
T ₄ (priming + NPK 5 g)	60.15	122.215
T ₅ (nonpriming + NPK 10 g)	30.19	81.513
T ₆ (priming + NPK 10 g)	48.95	108.345

Figure 22. Leaf Area of 57 DAS and 85 DAS

Treatment	All leaves fresh weight	3 leaves fresh weight	All stem fresh weight	All root fresh weight	The whole plant fresh weight
T ₁ Nonpriming	0.564	0.297	0.414	0.064	1.339
T ₂ Priming	0.627	0.389	0.451	0.061	1.528
T ₃ Nonpriming + NPK (5g)	1.288	0.463	1.086	0.182	3.019
T ₄ Priming + NPK(5g)	1.385	0.522	1.154	0.175	3.236
T ₅ Nonpriming + NPK (10g)	0.830	0.264	0.708	0.105	1.907
T ₆ Priming + NPK(10g)	0.980	0.427	0.640	0.114	2.161

Figure 23. Fresh weight (g) of 57 DAS

Table 13. Dry weight (g) of 57 DAS

Treatment	All leaves dry weight	3 leaves dry weight	All stem dry weight	All root dry weight	The whole plant dry weight
T ₁ Nonpriming	0.138	0.045	0.071	0.015	0.269
T ₂ Priming	0.160	0.055	0.092	0.019	0.326
T ₃ Nonpriming + NPK (5g)	0.237	0.122	0.131	0.038	0.528
T ₄ Priming + NPK(5g)	0.376	0.142	0.127	0.036	0.681
T ₅ Nonpriming + NPK (10g)	0.177	0.141	0.094	0.028	0.44
T ₆ Priming + NPK(10g)	0.187	0.153	0.096	0.027	0.463

Figure 24. Dry weight (g) of 57 DAS

Treatment	All leaves fresh weight	3 leaves fresh weight	All stem fresh weight	All root fresh weight	The whole plant fresh weight
T ₁ Nonpriming	1.586	0.758	1.612	0.287	4.243
T ₂ Priming	1.796	0.926	1.652	0.361	4.735
T ₃ Nonpriming + NPK (5g)	3.223	0.918	3.897	0.781	9.009
T ₄ Priming + NPK(5g)	4.285	1.208	4.903	1.468	11.864
T ₅ Nonpriming + NPK (10g)	2.702	0.818	3.647	0.718	7.885
T ₆ Priming + NPK(10g)	2.891	0.921	3.761	0.764	8.337

Figure 25. Fresh weight (g) of 85 DAS

Treatment	All leaves dry weight	3 leaves dry weight	All stem dry weight	All root dry weight	The whole plant dry weight
T ₁ Nonpriming	0.385	0.141	0.187	0.054	0.787
T ₂ Priming	0.396	0.153	0.198	0.067	0.814
T ₃ Nonpriming + NPK (5g)	1.075	0.146	0.217	0.068	1.506
T ₄ Priming + NPK(5g)	1.247	0.158	0.252	0.089	1.746
T ₅ Nonpriming + NPK (10g)	0.648	0.146	0.220	0.061	1.075
T ₆ Priming + NPK(10g)	0.659	0.152	0.227	0.068	1.106

Figure 26. Dry weight (g) of 85 DAS

Discussion and Conclusion

The rate of germination of *Capsicum frutescens* L. had more increased in priming seed than nonpriming seed.

The result showed that among priming and nonpriming of *Capsicum frutescens* L. plants with NPK fertilizers, T₄ treatment (priming + NPK 5g) had effect on growth of plants.

Out of 6 treatments, treatment T₄ revealed best results both in 57 DAS and 85 DAS. Although the same amount of given NPK 5g, the result T₄ is better than T₃ because treatment T₃ used nonpriming seeds.

In all treatments, except measurement of number of leaf per plants, all the rest treatment T₄ showed the optimum result.

The amount of NPK given 5g cannot be safely stated because the experiment many others uncontrolled variable such as soil temperature, soil moisture content, soil aeration etc. The best result can be stated only, when uncontrolled variable can be considered through multifactorial analysis.

In conclusion, the results of the experiments showed that the rate of germination of *Capsicum frutescens* L. plants with NPK fertilizers, T₄ treatment (priming + NPK 5g) had the superior development of plant height, leaf length, leaf width, leaf area, fresh weight and dry weight than other treatments. The number of leaf per plant in nonpriming more than in priming but the leaf size of nonpriming is smaller than that of priming.

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